

Delta Electron Spectroscopy: Energy and Angular Distributions in Metal Foils under Proton and Anti-proton Beams and GEANT4 Model Validation

Arman Khoshbakhti Vayeghan ArmanKhoshbakhti@gmail.com	Narges Yousefikhah nargesyosefikhah@gmail.com
Arshia Mirshamsi Kakhki arshia.mirshamsi1387@gmail.com	MohammadHossein Hosseini mhosseinium@gmail.com
Hiva Safaripour hivasafaripour@gmail.com	Alireza Heidari Mokarar Alireza4452alireza4452@gmail.com

March 2026

**To attend BL4S competition
Team DEEP (Delta-Electron Experimental Probe team)**

Abstract

This research is designed to precisely study the behavior of Delta Ray Electrons. We intend to observe the characteristics and most importantly, the distribution of the produced Delta-Electrons by exposing various metal foils -such as Aluminum, Copper, and Tungsten- to proton and anti-proton beams in CERN's Beamlines. The goal is to compare our experimental results with the four main physics models in GEANT4 (Standard, Livermore, Penelope, and Mott).

Furthermore, we will employ the Reduced Chi-square (χ_r^2) method to evaluate the accuracy of each model and selecting the best physics model for describing delta electrons in each energy range. At last, with this research we aim to validate different physics models in describing delta electrons and help optimize simulations.

Contents

1	Motivation	3
2	Introduction (Scientific basics)	3
2.1	What is Delta-Electron?	3
2.2	Important equations about Delta-Electrons	3
2.2.1	Energy loss equation (Bethe-Bloch)	3
2.2.2	Differential Cross Section (Probability) of Coulomb Interaction (Bethe formula)	5
2.2.3	Angular Distribution of Delta-Electrons (Rutherford Equation)	5
2.2.4	GEANT4 Physics Models	5
2.3	Data Analysis Methods	6
3	Proposal of the experiment	6
3.1	Experimental Variables and Measured Quantities	6
3.2	Experimental setup	7
3.3	Experimental procedure	8
3.3.1	Experimental process	8
3.3.2	Preparation and completion of tables	8
4	Outreach Activities	8
5	Acknowledgments	8
6	References	9
A	Experiments table	10

1 Motivation

These days, particle physics has become the gateway to understanding our modern universe, and in this quest for knowledge, CERN stands as a powerful symbol of global unity in research, dedicated to unraveling the mysteries of the world through innovation and experiment. Our team has delved into the particle physics world by studying relevant published papers with a deep focus on "ionization." This study raised questions such as: Is there a precise characterization for secondary electrons? How are they distributed? What is the difference between a delta-electron and a regular one? Does the CPT symmetry apply to them? (like the effect of gravity on them which CERN has been working on.)

These questions led us to conduct research, resulting in this experiment about the distribution of delta electrons and their energy. We are motivated to find our answers and test ourselves through the BL4S contest and hopefully achieve the opportunity to test our idea by accessing the Beamline available at CERN.

2 Introduction (Scientific basics)

2.1 What is Delta-Electron?

Delta ray electrons are no different from regular ones in terms of mass and electrical charge. However, they are produced when a high-energy ray passes through a metal foil (Figure 1). Electrons that are affected by the ray (electrons may be affected when rays pass near them) by the energy transferred between them, in a way that they are knocked off from the atom (Figure 2), are called delta electrons (Figure 3).

Figure 1: Electrons passing through copper foil.

2.2 Important equations about Delta-Electrons

2.2.1 Energy loss equation (Bethe-Bloch)

The mean energy loss by a particle that is charged z (in units of electron charge) and mass M moving through a material with density ρ is described with the Bethe-Bloch equation (Figure

Figure 2: Transferring path of affected electrons.

Figure 3: Energy of scattered electrons for Tungsten and Carbon rods.

4):

$$P = - \left\langle \frac{dE}{dx} \right\rangle = z^2 C \frac{Z}{A} \frac{\rho}{2\beta^2} \left(\ln \left(\frac{2m_e \beta^2 \gamma^2 T_{max}}{I^2(Z)} \right) - 2\beta^2 \right) \quad (1)$$

where T_{max} represents the maximum kinetic energy transferred in a single collision:

$$T_{max} = \frac{2m_e \beta^2 \gamma^2}{1 + \frac{2m_e \gamma}{M} + \left(\frac{m_e}{M}\right)^2} \quad (2)$$

But, if we have $M \gg m_e$, we can rewrite it like:

$$T_{max} \approx 2m_e c^2 \beta^2 \gamma^2 \quad (3)$$

where γ is the Lorentz factor and C is a constant defined as:

$$C = 4\pi N_a r_e^2 m_e \approx 0.307075 \frac{\text{MeV cm}^2}{\text{mol}} \quad (4)$$

This equation provides the value of energy loss as the beam travels through the material and, indicates the amount of energy loss the beam has; thus, it significantly contributes to the understanding of Delta-electron energy transfer.

Figure 4: Bethe-Bloch Equation

2.2.2 Differential Cross Section (Probability) of Coulomb Interaction (Bethe formula)

This equation determines the probability or cross section for the beam particle with kinetic energy of T to an electron:

$$\frac{d\sigma}{dT} = \frac{2\pi z^2 e^4}{m_e c^2 \beta^2} \frac{1}{T^2} \left(1 - \beta^2 \frac{T}{T_{max}} + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{T}{E} \right)^2 \right) \quad (5)$$

In this equation, e represents the electron charge, and the remaining definitions are as said in the previous section.

Also, for counting Delta-Electrons we can integrate over T and express the equation like this:

$$\frac{dN_\delta}{dx} = n_e \int_{T_{cutoff}}^{T_{max}} \frac{d\sigma}{dT} dT \quad (6)$$

2.2.3 Angular Distribution of Delta-Electrons (Rutherford Equation)

The Rutherford equation, which is based on his famous gold foil experiment in 1911 and his atomic model hypothesis, approximately shows us the scattering angle of delta electrons (θ) to the direction of the incident beam:

$$\frac{d\sigma}{d\Omega} = \left(\frac{zZe^2}{8\pi\epsilon_0 E} \frac{1}{\sin^2(\theta/2)} \right)^2 \quad (7)$$

Of course, assuming that the particle is classical (non-relativistic), we have $T = \frac{1}{2}mv^2 = \frac{p^2}{2m} = \frac{pv}{2}$ and the equation appears in the following form:

$$\frac{d\sigma}{d\Omega} = \left(\frac{Zze^2}{4\pi\epsilon_0 pv} \frac{1}{\sin^2(\theta/2)} \right)^2 \quad (8)$$

2.2.4 GEANT4 Physics Models

In computer simulations such as GEANT4, various models exist for describing electromagnetic interactions and the production of Delta-electrons. These models often differ in corrective terms or their application across different energy ranges. We examine the following four models:

- **G4EmStandardPhysics_option4 (Standard Model):** Performs well across a wide spectrum of energies.
- **G4EmLivermorePhysics (Livermore Model):** Is significantly more accurate at low energies (less than 1 GeV).
- **G4EmPenelopePhysics (Penelope Model):** Possesses high accuracy across low and medium energy ranges.
- **G4EmStandardPhysics_option3 (Mott Scattering Model):** This model accurately simulates Mott scattering.

2.3 Data Analysis Methods

To select the superior physics model, one must resort to data analysis. One of the most common methods for model selection is the reduced chi-square method (χ^2_ν); such that the model with the lower reduced chi-square value is considered more accurate.

$$\chi^2_\nu = \frac{\chi^2}{\nu}$$

$$\chi^2 = \sum_i (x_{exp,i} - x_{th,i})^2$$

In these equations, ν represents the number of data points minus the degrees of freedom, $x_{exp,i}$ is the value obtained from the experiment for data point i , and $x_{th,i}$ is the value obtained from the theory for the same data point i .

3 Proposal of the experiment

3.1 Experimental Variables and Measured Quantities

Independent Variables:

1. Foil Material: Aluminum ($Z = 13$), Copper ($Z = 29$), Tungsten ($Z = 74$).
2. Beam Momentum: Very low momentum (~ 0.5 GeV/ c), relatively low momentum (~ 2 GeV/ c), medium momentum (~ 6 GeV/ c), high momentum (~ 10 GeV/ c), very high momentum (~ 15 GeV/ c).
3. Beam Type: Mixed positive particles (protons, etc.) or mixed negative particles (anti-protons, etc.).

Measured Quantities:

1. **Number of Delta-Electrons in Each Angular Interval ($N(\theta)$):** The count of delta electrons within the intervals of 0 to 5 degrees, 5 to 10 degrees, 10 to 20 degrees, 20 to 30 degrees, 30 to 45 degrees, 45 to 60 degrees, and 60 to 90 degrees.
2. **Average Energy of Delta-Electrons in Each Angular Interval ($\bar{E}(\theta)$):** The average energy of delta electrons scattered at the mentioned angular intervals.

3.2 Experimental setup

The experimental design is customized to simplify the precise measurement of the angle and energy of delta electrons. Our setup consists the following elements:

1. **Beam:** We require mixed beams with positive and negative charges, as provided by CERN.
2. **Trigger system:** To filter the beams and select protons or antiprotons (in positive or negative beams), a trigger system is required. A common design for this system is Time of Flight System (ToF). We have designed this system that considering the beam's fix momentum (as explained in the Beams & Detectors file that you shared in website), a theoretical time difference of approximately 170 ps is created between protons and other particles. To separate this time difference, we use Fast Plastic Scintillators (like BC-418 model, with a time resolution of 150 ps, which is good for our needs). So, two detectors are placed opposite each other to measure time differences, and a trigger accept command is issued to our data acquisition module(Considering module) only if the measured ToF corresponds to the specific time of flight of the proton(or antiproton).
3. **Target Wheel:** To optimize time usage, our team decided to design a simple wheel that allows us to easy changing of the target material with a 120-degree rotation. The base height is 1.5 meters, the wheel diameter is 1 meter and each foil piece is 30×30 cm. Also, the thickness of foils will match with Rutherford's thin foil regime (approximately 0.5% to 1% of the proton ionization range in the material). Assuming the average energy of the beam about 5 GeV, the thickness will be approximately 1 to 2 mm for Aluminum, 0.5 to 1 mm for Copper, and 0.1 to 0.3 mm for Tungsten.
4. **DWC Detectors:** These 10×10 cm detectors provide the position of every passing particle with good spatial accuracy (200 to 300 micrometers). Also, these detectors have a time resolution of approximately 700 ps, which is good for our experiment.

Figure 5: General schematic of the setup

3.3 Experimental procedure

3.3.1 Experimental process

At the beginning of the experimental beamline, a Trigger System is placed, which allows protons to pass for the positive beam, and antiprotons for the negative beam. The resulting beam then reaches the fixed target (Aluminum, Copper, and Tungsten foil), and according to theory, the desired Delta-electrons are produced. On the target wheel, all three target foils are installed to enable changing experimental conditions. As previously mentioned, the goal of the experiment is to measure the quantities of $\bar{E}(\theta)$ and $N(\theta)$ for the proposed angular ranges. To measure $N(\theta)$, we apply an array of two-dimensional DWC detectors (Delay Wire Chambers), and to measure $\bar{E}(\theta)$, we apply an array of calorimeters placed around the target at various angles. Subsequently, two measurement methods are available for us. The first, more accurate method includes measuring $\bar{E}(\theta)$ and $N(\theta)$ in separate experiments. The duration of each experiment must be long enough to detect a suitable number of Delta-electrons (approximately 10^4). Assuming the production rate of Delta electrons from the primary beam is about 1%, and there are approximately 10^4 to 10^5 particles in each beam spill with a beam rate of approximately 1spill/min, the time required for each experiment will be around 10 to 100 minutes. Given these conditions, and considering that we examine $\bar{E}(\theta)$ and N for three different targets across five momentum ranges for protons and antiprotons, we must perform 60 experiments to complete our measurements. This will take between 10hours in the most optimistic scenario and 100hours in the most pessimistic one. This time frame easily fits within our scheduled time at CERN, accounting for device setup and rest periods. The second method involves performing the experiments by placing both DWCs and calorimeters in the setup simultaneously to measure energy and count at the same time. This simultaneous measurement would reduce the duration of our experiments to half. However, since we know that the energy of delta-electrons changes as they pass through the DWC detectors, we prefer to use the first method, which offers higher precision for our measurements.

3.3.2 Preparation and completion of tables

The tables placed in Appendix A will be completed following the experiment; however, they are presented here to clarify the objectives and experimental methods for the reviewers.

4 Outreach Activities

Our team is planning for two important dates: International Science Day and International Astronomy Day. These are significant events in Iran, celebrated by people to showcase their achievements and knowledge in multiple scientific fields through public speeches and performances. However, this goal can only be achieved once our experiment is completed at CERN, which unfortunately means we will not be able to participate in International Astronomy Day 2026(April 29). But hopefully we will be able to finish this project and participate in 2027.

5 Acknowledgments

We would like to mention that BL4S has become more than just an academic experiment but a journey full of teamwork and patience for us. Most importantly, it has helped us develop brand new friendships that will never be forgotten. We are also deeply grateful to our coaches Parsa Sadeghi and Aria Hemmatian for their unwavering support during this project. We also extend our special thanks to Hadi Khaleghi for designing some of the graphics used in this work. Last but not least, we must acknowledge that completing this work during these critical times in Iran has been a profound challenge. We have endured the loss of family and friends, and on top

of that, we have faced and are facing severe internet restrictions, with our access being cut off for 60 to 70 percent of the time dedicated to this project. Despite these obstacles and the high stress of meeting the deadline with limited connectivity, we remained committed to our work. We are submitting this proposal through unimaginable means to bypass restrictions, with hopes of being able to test our theories in CERN.

6 References

References

- [1] Beamline for schools competition. (2026). *CERN Official Website*. Retrieved from <https://beamline-for-schools.web.cern.ch/>
- [2] Particle Data Group. (2022). *Passage of particles through matter (Review of Particle Physics)*. Lawrence Berkeley National laboratory
- [3] Khan, S. (2021). *Handbook of Particle Physics*. CRC Press
- [4] Leo, W. R. (2010). *Techniques for Nuclear and Physics Experiments: A How-to Approach*. Springer-Verlag, Berlin.
- [5] Knoll, G. F. (2022). *Radiation Detection and Measurement*. John Wiley & Sons.
- [6] Bethe, H. (1934). On the stopping of fast particles and on the creation of positive electrons. *Proceedings of the Royal Society of London*.
- [7] Allison, J. (2016). Recent improvements in GEANT4. *A*, 835, 186-225
- [8] Agostinelli, S. et al. (2003). GEANT4—a simulation toolkit. *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research A*.

A Experiments table

Beam Momentum	Material →								
	Al			Cu			W		
	Angle	N	E	Angle	N	E	Angle	N	E
Very low 0.5 GeV/c	[0°,5°)			[0°,5°)			[0°,5°)		
	[5°,10°)			[5°,10°)			[5°,10°)		
	[10°,20°)			[10°,20°)			[10°,20°)		
	[20°,30°)			[20°,30°)			[20°,30°)		
	[30°,45°)			[30°,45°)			[30°,45°)		
	[45°,60°)			[45°,60°)			[45°,60°)		
	[60°,90°)			[60°,90°)			[60°,90°)		
Low 2 GeV/c	[0°,5°)			[0°,5°)			[0°,5°)		
	[5°,10°)			[5°,10°)			[5°,10°)		
	[10°,20°)			[10°,20°)			[10°,20°)		
	[20°,30°)			[20°,30°)			[20°,30°)		
	[30°,45°)			[30°,45°)			[30°,45°)		
	[45°,60°)			[45°,60°)			[45°,60°)		
	[60°,90°)			[60°,90°)			[60°,90°)		
Medium 6 GeV/c	[0°,5°)			[0°,5°)			[0°,5°)		
	[5°,10°)			[5°,10°)			[5°,10°)		
	[10°,20°)			[10°,20°)			[10°,20°)		
	[20°,30°)			[20°,30°)			[20°,30°)		
	[30°,45°)			[30°,45°)			[30°,45°)		
	[45°,60°)			[45°,60°)			[45°,60°)		
	[60°,90°)			[60°,90°)			[60°,90°)		

Table 1: Data Table for Positive Beam Momentum and Materials (Lower Beam Momentum Values)

Beam Momentum	Material →								
	Al			Cu			W		
	Angle	N	E	Angle	N	E	Angle	N	E
High 10 GeV/c	[0°,5°)			[0°,5°)			[0°,5°)		
	[5°,10°)			[5°,10°)			[5°,10°)		
	[10°,20°)			[10°,20°)			[10°,20°)		
	[20°,30°)			[20°,30°)			[20°,30°)		
	[30°,45°)			[30°,45°)			[30°,45°)		
	[45°,60°)			[45°,60°)			[45°,60°)		
	[60°,90°)			[60°,90°)			[60°,90°)		
Very high 15 GeV/c	[0°,5°)			[0°,5°)			[0°,5°)		
	[5°,10°)			[5°,10°)			[5°,10°)		
	[10°,20°)			[10°,20°)			[10°,20°)		
	[20°,30°)			[20°,30°)			[20°,30°)		
	[30°,45°)			[30°,45°)			[30°,45°)		
	[45°,60°)			[45°,60°)			[45°,60°)		
	[60°,90°)			[60°,90°)			[60°,90°)		

Table 2: Data Table for Positive Beam Momentum and Materials (Higher Beam Momentum Values)

Beam Momentum	Material →								
	Al			Cu			W		
	Angle	N	E	Angle	N	E	Angle	N	E
Very low 0.5 GeV/c	[0°,5°)			[0°,5°)			[0°,5°)		
	[5°,10°)			[5°,10°)			[5°,10°)		
	[10°,20°)			[10°,20°)			[10°,20°)		
	[20°,30°)			[20°,30°)			[20°,30°)		
	[30°,45°)			[30°,45°)			[30°,45°)		
	[45°,60°)			[45°,60°)			[45°,60°)		
	[60°,90°)			[60°,90°)			[60°,90°)		
Low 2 GeV/c	[0°,5°)			[0°,5°)			[0°,5°)		
	[5°,10°)			[5°,10°)			[5°,10°)		
	[10°,20°)			[10°,20°)			[10°,20°)		
	[20°,30°)			[20°,30°)			[20°,30°)		
	[30°,45°)			[30°,45°)			[30°,45°)		
	[45°,60°)			[45°,60°)			[45°,60°)		
	[60°,90°)			[60°,90°)			[60°,90°)		
Medium 6 GeV/c	[0°,5°)			[0°,5°)			[0°,5°)		
	[5°,10°)			[5°,10°)			[5°,10°)		
	[10°,20°)			[10°,20°)			[10°,20°)		
	[20°,30°)			[20°,30°)			[20°,30°)		
	[30°,45°)			[30°,45°)			[30°,45°)		
	[45°,60°)			[45°,60°)			[45°,60°)		
	[60°,90°)			[60°,90°)			[60°,90°)		

Table 3: Data Table for Negative Beam Momentum and Materials (Lower Beam Momentum Values)

Beam Momentum	Material →								
	Al			Cu			W		
	Angle	N	E	Angle	N	E	Angle	N	E
High 10 GeV/c	[0°,5°)			[0°,5°)			[0°,5°)		
	[5°,10°)			[5°,10°)			[5°,10°)		
	[10°,20°)			[10°,20°)			[10°,20°)		
	[20°,30°)			[20°,30°)			[20°,30°)		
	[30°,45°)			[30°,45°)			[30°,45°)		
	[45°,60°)			[45°,60°)			[45°,60°)		
	[60°,90°)			[60°,90°)			[60°,90°)		
Very high 15 GeV/c	[0°,5°)			[0°,5°)			[0°,5°)		
	[5°,10°)			[5°,10°)			[5°,10°)		
	[10°,20°)			[10°,20°)			[10°,20°)		
	[20°,30°)			[20°,30°)			[20°,30°)		
	[30°,45°)			[30°,45°)			[30°,45°)		
	[45°,60°)			[45°,60°)			[45°,60°)		
	[60°,90°)			[60°,90°)			[60°,90°)		

Table 4: Data Table for Negative Beam Momentum and Materials (Higher Beam Momentum Values)